

CLASSIFICATION OF PEDAGOGICAL TERMS IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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Annotation.

A word in the national language becomes a pedagogical terminology whenever it begins to denote a scientific concept of pedagogical facts, phenomena, processes, events that together with others concepts in the field of pedagogy and education one semantic system. Pedagogical terminology, together with nominally pedagogical concepts, moves from language to language and contributes to the creation of international pedagogical terminology, ensuring international scientific communication, optimal mutual understanding and interaction. In this aspect, international pedagogical terminology performs the function of systematization of disparate national and regional pedagogical terms and terminological systems.

Keywords: pedagogical terminology, international pedagogical terminology, special education terminology, pedagogical science, ESL, EFL, TESL, TEFL, TEFL certificate, TESL / TESOL Certification.

International pedagogical terminology is associative, multilateral, multidimensional nature, including general information about pedagogy as a science and deep concepts associated with certain narrow areas in the theory and practice of world pedagogical science. The international pedagogical terminology reveals its own kind of different connections between culturally determined pedagogical activity: traditional and innovative. It fixes information about its new sides and perspectives, specific socio-cultural circumstances reflecting the features of the development of world pedagogical science and practice of education, scientific and educational regions, local pedagogical cultures and languages (G.A. Ferguson, M.L. Anderson \ The Ins and Outs of Special Education Terminology.

Normative Aspect of International Pedagogical Terminology finds expression in the consolidation of the selected optimal pedagogical terms and their definitions by normative documents and prescriptions (teaching aids, pedagogical rubricators, classifiers, terminological recommendations, normative dictionaries, editorial instructions, and others). Diversified research and practical activities using various information and communication technology contributes to the identification of characteristic of modern the state of the international

pedagogical terminology of processes, i.e. the most typical and more often others implemented, among which:

- a change in the volume of the composition of international pedagogical terminology, namely, its expansion through the inclusion of terms and terminological phrases from other areas of knowledge;
- a change in the rate of renewal of international pedagogical terminology as a result of the obsolescence of some terms and the intensive filling of international pedagogical terminology with new terminological units;
- extensive structural changes in international pedagogical terminology, caused by the growth of new terms and terminological phrases, adapted by local pedagogical cultures from world pedagogy and adjacent areas of scientific knowledge;
- variability of international pedagogical terminology, lack of unity of terminology describing research processes at the global level and at the level of local pedagogical cultures;
- active "introduction" of new terms as a result of creative comprehension of the picture of the world, their intensive interpretation from the standpoint of subjective and culturally conditioned pedagogical perception of the world and world reflection;
- the desire to overcome scientific fragmentation is natural established terminologies associated with national systems;
- the formation of new, not previously identified relationships between specialized scientific and pedagogical knowledge (knowledge of the field of research), professional language (the language of professional pedagogical communication) and pedagogical terminology from the point of view of pedagogical concepts and their representation in the subject area;
- development of research aimed at identifying trends in the processes of functioning of terms in local pedagogical systems and their interaction at the global level;

So, for example, at present, pedagogical science is actively global computer networks based on telecommunication technologies are being introduced. There is a trend towards a gradual change in traditional information environment for computer telecommunications, active introduction of information and communication technologies into educational practice and professional pedagogical interaction. However, today one of the problems of using computer and communication technologies is the distortion of terminology, and in some cases irreparable loss of information (the effect of semantic filters). This is due to

the fact that terminology in the field of computer communications, architecture of computer networks, software for computer telecommunications, computer user interface and computer networks has not yet been established, For example, computer telecommunications (computer telecommunications), telematics (teleinformatics)), educational telecomputing, computer networks (network, networking), dynamic Web-resource, information utilities, etc. Many terms have ambiguous interpretations and often associated with technical means are not adapted as terms of pedagogical science and educational practice. So, for example, visual elements of hypertext structures WWW documents that the teacher-user of computer networks directly encounters are given less attention than technical aspects and software support. Terminology, for example in the field of computer-assisted language learning (Computer-Assisted Language Learning) has not yet become part of a unified pedagogical thesaurus in this area (M. Bovtenko). For example, one of the activities of such an international organization as TESOL (<www.tesol.org>) is aimed at harmonizing international pedagogical terminology in the field of teaching English as a foreign language, creating a situation in which there will be a common understanding of specialists in this field, representing different countries and different linguistic communities. So, for example, the Starting Your Career in TESOL page explains the difference between key terms requiring a single understanding, such as ESL, EFL, TESL, TEFL, TEFL certificate, TESL / TESOL Certification, add-on endorsement, ELT (English Language teaching or training), ESOL.

The components of the projected model of *international pedagogical terminology* can be represented by separate terms, national terminological systems that describe various areas and sections of pedagogical theory and practice of education. For example, such as: national educational systems; higher education; curricula; programs; quality of educational opportunity; educational achievement; evaluation and examinations; intercultural education; the treatment of minority groups; women in education; formal, nonformal and informal education; delivery modes; teacher training; certification and supply; citizenship education; politics, ideology, and schooling; language and literacy; schooling, and the economy; education modernization, and development; education reform; accountability; effective schooling; school administration and governance.

The need to use the seed method is dictated by the need to isolate a set of meaningful indicators, presented in the form of semes, transmitting certain terminological meanings and containing the basis for the emergence of

conceptual relationships between terms, which are more definite and clear than the relationship between commonly used words due to the systematic nature of the term (V.D. Tabanakov). For example: *Higher Education* (Admission / Enrollment / Entrance; Adult Education / Continuing Education / Further Education / Extension Courses; Baccalaureate / Bachelor's Degree / Bachelor; Comprehensive Exams / Comprehensives / Comps; Degree (Academic / Associate / Bachelor's / Doctor's / Degree / First Professional / Honorary / Master's / Specialist, etc.); *Intercultural (multicultural) Education* (acculturation; adaptation; attraction theory; communication (communication competence, pragmatics, strategies of communication: compliance-gaining strategies, compliance-resisting strategies, etc.); communicator (characteristics); conflict; cultural conflict; culture; cultural assimilation; cultural display; cultural distance; culture shock; enculturation; empathy; intercultural communication; nonverbal and verbal communication; self-awareness; self-fulfilling prophecy; stereotype. The principle of self-organization and self-development contains a recommendation to consider the object of modeling, i.e., international pedagogical terminology, as a self-organizing and self-developing phenomenon. For example, in the English-language pedagogical literature recently.

Since then, in connection with the processes of globalization, the formation of market relations in educational systems, terms have begun to appear that capture these tendencies. These are terms like "*Higher Learning Industry*". *Global Learning Services*", "*Commonwealth of Learning*", "*Mega Universities*" and narrower terms associated with them and detailing their content, for example: corporate university, student clientele, networked university system, chief executive officer (instead of Vice-Chancellor), new methods of delivery. The modeling process should reveal tendencies, internal mechanisms and reserves for the development of such terminology. Consolidating the latest trends in world pedagogical science and educational practice. It is important that the simulated future state of the system coincided with the trajectory of the system reaching the stage of its evolutionary development and the coordination of individual multilingual terms and term systems. In this aspect, the simulated international pedagogical terminology becomes the main link connecting research and educational activities, science and practice, local and global achievements (M. Schlick, O. Neurath, F. Weismann, R. Kanrap). A network representation of the international model *pedagogical terminology* (R. Carnap) has not only a purely applied meaning, but also allows one to penetrate deeper into the system of logic of pedagogical science, more precisely to model terminological systems and their

connections in separate directions and pedagogical cultures. For example: *Education*: Adult, Career and Vocational (Continuing Education \ Adult Literacy Education Volunteer-based Education \ Community-based literacy programs. Programs designed for language minority adults \ Career counselor \ Low-literate, educationally disadvantaged and educationally oppressed people \ Self-learning, etc); Business Education; Communication Education (Communication Instruction \ Methodology, Approach and Setting \ Instructional context \ Variety of delivery media (face-to-face, computer-mediated, video) \ Communication theory \ Communication studies); Community education; Comparative Studies; Curriculum Studies; Disabled and Gifted Education; Education Economics; Education Management \ Administration; Education Primary, Secondary, Tertiary, Higher, etc. (see: List of Educational Terms compiled as a result of the findings of a quantitative study of ELT Theory, Research and Practice Related Terminology in the Proceedings of TESOL-2001 Convention and Cabell's Directory of Publishing Opportunities in Education. Volumes 1 & 2 Fifth Edition 1998-1999 // Workbook, Rostov-on-Don, 2001).

In international pedagogical terminology, there are two main layers of terms. On the one hand, these are terms denoting pedagogical concepts, on the other hand, pedagogical nomenclature, or designations of the names of single pedagogical phenomena or subjects of pedagogical research. Linguistic formalization of scientific and pedagogical concepts, developed in the world theory and practice of education, their translation and adaptation, sequential definitive processing of the "sections" of pedagogy and pedagogical theories, fixing their spatial and temporal dynamics in lexicographic sources and information resources.

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